

LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY.

Muradov Sirojiddin

Siddiqova Madinabonu

Karimov Bahodir

Intern-teacher of the Department of "Labor Protection and Technical Safety" of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics.

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Abstract. *In this article, the main indicators of the efficiency of labor protection measures in the field of labor protection and technical safety are studied from the theoretical and analytical point of view, and theoretical methods of labor protection measures and methods are reflected.*

Key Words: *"Labor protection, technical safety, labor legislation, psychophysiology, physical activity, working time, work mode, occupational diseases, labor productivity."*

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПО ОХРАНЕ ТРУДА.

Аннотация. *В данной статье с теоретико-аналитической точки зрения исследованы основные показатели эффективности мероприятий по охране труда в области охраны труда и технической безопасности, а также отражены теоретические методы и методы проведения мероприятий по охране труда.*

Ключевые слова: *«Охрана труда, техническая безопасность, трудовое законодательство, психофизиология, физическая активность, рабочее время, режим труда, профессиональные заболевания, производительность труда».*

INTRODUCTION. Systematic work is being carried out in our country in order to ensure that employees work in healthy and safe workplaces and to further improve the labor protection of employees. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Labor Protection" adopted in the new version (in the new version) is proof of our opinion.

Today, based on the requirements of the new version of the Law "On Labor Protection", drafts of legal documents on creating safe working conditions for employees are being developed.

In particular, "Model Regulation on the organization of labor protection in the organization", "Model Regulation on the organization's labor protection service" by experts on labor protection of the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan and the Republican Councils of branch trade unions ", "Regulation on the training, retraining and upgrading of labor protection specialists", "Regulation on the audit of the labor protection management system in the organization", "Professional regulation of the market of services in the field of labor protection

"Regulation on State Expertise of Labor Conditions", "Regulation on Inspection and Registration of Occupational Diseases" drafts were thoroughly studied and relevant proposals were prepared.

Adaptation of these legal documents to the new version of the Law will, first of all, ensure the effective and correct organization of labor protection at the level of the republic, sector and region. Also, together with the employer, it increases the responsibility of the employee in terms of labor protection, and increases the interest of the employer in the proper organization of activities in the field of labor protection without the intervention of state control bodies. The most important thing is that the efficiency of prevention of occupational diseases and industrial accidents increases, thereby further development of the economy of the organization and strengthening of social protection of employees is achieved.

As a result of the implemented reforms, the role of creating decent working conditions for employees of all sectors of the economy is incomparable, and the legal framework is an important factor in this. The new version of the Law "On Labor Protection" entered into force on December 24, 2016 is an important document in this sense, as it is aimed at solving a number of issues.

For example, it increases the responsibility of the employer and employees for the fulfillment of the requirements for labor protection, including hiding the cases of accidents that occurred in production or not conducting its timely inspection, the implementation of the conditions of labor protection a number of other rules are provided, such as putting an end to cases of failure to provide the instructions of the supervising state body within the specified time.

At this point, it is permissible to dwell on some specific aspects of the law. In accordance with its separate article, a labor protection service is established or a specialist position with appropriate training in labor protection is introduced in every organization that carries out production activities and has fifty or more employees.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS OBTAINED. Specialists of the labor protection service monitor compliance with labor protection rules and norms by all employees, issue mandatory instructions to the heads of structural units to eliminate identified violations, as well as labor protection issues has the right to make submissions to the head of the organization about bringing to responsibility persons who violate the requirements of regulatory documents and regulatory legal documents. These tasks can also be performed by professional participants of the market of services in this field on the basis of a contract.

According to the law, legal entities that provide services on the basis of a labor protection contract are professional participants in the market of services in this field. They can carry out the tasks of the labor protection service in organizations, conduct attestation of workplaces according

to working conditions, retrain specialists and improve their qualifications, conduct an audit of the labor protection management system. The Cabinet of Ministers shall determine the requirements for the professional participants of the market of services in the field of labor protection and the requirements for the performance of services by them, as well as the procedure for maintaining their unified register.

As noted in a separate article, the attestation of working conditions of workplaces is in the field of technical regulation of labor protection issues of working conditions, as well as the severity and intensity of the labor process in workplaces and their danger in terms of injury. It is a set of activities conducted in order to assess the compliance with the requirements of regulatory documents and regulatory legal documents, to determine the harmful or dangerous production factor. From the attestation of workplaces on working conditions, productions, institutions, works, professions, positions, etc., where benefits and compensations are provided for employees according to the working conditions in accordance with the procedure established by law, where disabled people are employed, and who give the right to retire on preferential terms Jobs specified in the lists of indicators, jobs in hazardous production facilities should be transferred.

Such attestation is carried out by the employer himself in the prescribed manner. The periodicity of this attestation is determined by legislation, but it should be at least once every five years.

The norm on the audit of the labor protection management system can be said to be one of the special aspects of the law. This audit is an assessment of the state of the labor protection system, which is carried out according to the decision of the employer. The audit will determine whether the labor protection management system in the organization is technically compliant with the requirements of regulatory documents and regulatory legal documents on these issues, the quality of the labor protection management system, the effectiveness of measures aimed at preventing and reducing the level of injuries and occupational diseases in production. evaluation, includes the development of proposals and recommendations aimed at eliminating identified deficiencies, preventing injuries and occupational diseases in production. The audit is performed by professional participants of the market of services in the field of labor protection on the basis of a contract.

In the state management of labor protection, the powers of the Cabinet of Ministers, the specially authorized state body in this field - the Ministry of Labor, as well as the Ministry of Health, state and economic management bodies, and local state authorities related to the field of labor protection are specified in the law.

The most important thing is that the norms of this law are in accordance with the conventions and recommendations of the International Labor Organization and the world standards, and ensure the correct organization of labor protection at the level of the republic, sector and region, and the employer and employees in relation to the fulfillment of labor protection requirements. It will undoubtedly serve to increase the interest of the employer in the correct implementation of the measures in the field of labor protection, prevention and reduction of occupational diseases and accidents in production.

Measures to improve working conditions and labor protection include all economic activities aimed at preventing, ending or reducing the negative impact of harmful and dangerous production factors on workers. These activities can be single-purpose and multi-purpose. Single-purpose measures are fully or mainly aimed at improving working conditions and labor protection. Multi-purpose activities improve the working conditions and increase the level of safety while improving the results of production activities of enterprises. Such activities include, for example, automation of technological process management, mechanization of manual work, introduction of new advanced machines and mechanisms, etc.

Four groups of indicators are currently proposed to evaluate the results of measures to improve working conditions and labor protection: changes in working conditions; social; socio-economic; economic.

Changes in working conditions at workplaces are evaluated: improvement of the level of work safety, improvement of sanitary-hygienic indicators, improvement of psychophysiological indicators, improvement of aesthetic indicators.

The increase in the level of labor safety is characterized by the increase of machines, mechanisms and production buildings in accordance with the requirements of standards, labor safety and construction standards and regulations.

Improvement of sanitary indicators is characterized by reducing the amount of harmful substances in the air, improving the microclimate, reducing the level of noise and vibration, reducing infrasonic and ultrasonic vibrations, ionizing and electromagnetic radiation, ultraviolet and infrared radiation; improve lighting.

Improvement of psychophysiological indicators is characterized by reduction of physical and neuropsychiatric loads, including monotony of work.

Improvement of aesthetic indicators is characterized by rationalization of workplaces and machines; improvement of buildings and enterprise territory, color finishing of equipment and interiors, etc.

Changes in the state of the production environment for the specified factors with the difference between their absolute values before and after the measures, as well as the maximum permissible concentrations, the maximum permissible levels or the relative level describing the degree of compliance of certain factors with the specified levels can be evaluated by comparing indicators. A comprehensive assessment of the state of working conditions is carried out with the growth of jobs in the complex, where the working conditions are in accordance with regulatory requirements.

The social results of the implementation of measures for the improvement of conditions and labor protection are described as the difference in natural values before and after the implementation of the measures according to the following indicators:

- increasing the number of employees whose jobs meet regulatory requirements in accordance with working conditions or reducing non-compliant jobs (in terms of individual factors and the complex));
- reduction of industrial injuries;
- reduction of occupational and general morbidity caused by unfavorable working conditions;
- decrease in personnel turnover due to dissatisfaction with working conditions.

Other indicators can be used to assess social outcomes, such as job satisfaction, increasing the prestige of professions, but only after their reliable quantitative evaluation methods have been developed. Some of the social outcomes can be expressed in the form of savings in labor time and money. Such indicators have a dual character from a socio-economic point of view.

Socio-economic results are expressed in the form of preventing or preventing the loss of living and moral labor in the national economy, enterprises and personal consumption.

An economic approach is needed in the evaluation of socio-economic results, that is, a more complete coverage of all social and economic results in various sectors of the economy, as well as time factors can be taken into account in the evaluation of costs and results of activities.

Economic results are determined by calculating three main indicators: net economic impact, total economic efficiency and comparative economic efficiency.

The net economic impact indicator means the difference between the economic results that lead to the annual measurement and the costs of their implementation. It is calculated in cases of economic justification of all measures and is applied to: justify the expected (calculated)

impact of scientific and project decisions on improving conditions and labor protection; choosing the most effective options of two or more activities that differ in terms of their impact on the indicators of the production environment, as well as on their social and economic results; economic evaluation of the activities actually carried out, in particular, determination of the size of financial incentives for the improvement of working conditions and work in the field of labor protection of employees of enterprises, scientific research and project organizations.

Economic results are characterized by the economic impact of measures to prevent accidents, injuries and occupational diseases, improve hygiene, technical and social conditions.

The economic impact is calculated and used in cases of economic justification of all measures: to justify the expected (calculated) impact of scientific and project decisions on improving conditions and labor protection; selection of the most effective options of two or more activities that affect the indicators of the production environment, as well as their social and economic results; economic evaluation of effective activity.

CONCLUSION. The indicator of general economic efficiency is the ratio of economic results to costs. It is calculated in cases of economic justification of all measures and is used to determine the costs of improving conditions and labor protection; determining the dynamics of economic efficiency; comparative analysis of cost efficiency in different enterprises, economic sectors and regions; comparison of expected (calculated) and actual economic efficiency with approved standards.

The efficiency index (coefficient) of capital investments should be compared with regulation ($en = 0.08$). If $EC > en$, capital investment can be considered efficient

The return period of capital investments should be compared with the normative ($tn = 12.5$ years), if it is less than the regulation, capital investments are considered effective.

Indicators of economic efficiency of measures to improve working conditions and increase their safety are as follows:

- reduce losses due to accidents, fires, injuries and morbidity;
- benefits obtained as a result of increasing labor productivity related to the improvement of medical-biological and technological-technical conditions;
- reduce losses by reducing employee turnover, improve working conditions;
- saving raw materials, materials, energy in the use of equipment used as a means of collective protection;
- reducing costs associated with providing benefits and compensation for workers working in harmful working conditions;

- determining efficiency by reducing irrational loss of working time;
- determining efficiency by reducing compensatory rest;
- to determine the saving of the wage fund in connection with the reduction of additional payments to the tariff rate according to labor conditions;
- to determine the saving of the wage fund in connection with the cancellation of the shortened working day according to the working conditions.

The indicator of comparative economic efficiency of two activities is defined as the difference of costs allocated to these activities, taking into account the time factor. Comparable options are calculated in cases that allow to achieve the same quality of the production environment and have the same social and economic results. On the basis of this indicator, it is necessary to choose the option of actions that allow to achieve the desired state of the production environment with minimum costs.

In order to improve the conditions and economic justification of labor protection measures, the following is necessary:

- selection of initial information about the state of the production environment, achieved social results, technical and economic indicators of the main and implemented capabilities of the enterprise (industry);
- determining the costs of implementation of activities;
- calculation of social and socio-economic efficiency, activity;
- calculate the full economic impact, that is, the economic results of the implementation of the activity;
- calculate the net economic impact, total and comparative efficiency indicators.

The increase in the level of labor safety is characterized by the increase of machines, mechanisms and production buildings in accordance with the requirements of standards, labor safety and construction standards and regulations.

The following socio-economic indicators can be used to assess the social impact of the implementation of labor protection and improvement of working conditions:

1. Reducing the number of workplaces that do not meet the standard requirements of sanitary and hygienic working conditions.
2. Reducing the number of workers in conditions that do not meet sanitary and hygienic standards.

3. Increasing the number of machines, mechanisms and production rooms brought in accordance with the requirements of sanitary hygiene standards and other regulatory and technical documents.

4. Reduction of industrial injuries.

5. Reduce morbidity.

6. Reduction in cases of disability due to trauma or illness.

7. Reducing staff turnover due to unfavorable working conditions.

8. Saving of working time for one employee due to the reduction of staff turnover.

The social impact on these indicators is calculated as the difference of the indicators before and after the activities, as it is indicated in the methodological instructions.

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